

MISSION DETERMINES EQUALITY BETWEEN RADARS

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ABSTRACT

Forty-three L-Band radars will be deployed on the periphery of the United States for joint use by the United States Air Force and the Federal Aviation Administration. The unattended radar system is designed to scan a range of 250 nautical miles up to an altitude of 100,000 feet, with look-down capability from high sites. The radar must detect fast, small radar cross-section aircraft in a realistic man-made and natural interference environment (including thousands of flocks of birds), while minimizing false alarms. The radar must also generate weather intensity contours.

This paper describes trade-offs that were made in the process of selecting and designing a system architecture that needed to serve two different users with different mission requirements. It also gives guidelines for off-the-shelf purchases and planning for future growth in mission requirements.

INTRODUCTION

The fact that "All radars are not created equal" can become painfully evident when trying to purchase off-the-shelf equipment to satisfy unique mission requirements. This paper will give examples of the decisions that must be made when choosing a radar architecture. It will also show that a radar's mission definition is more important in the acquisition process than its individual performance specification. Because a radar's mission is about 70 percent dependent on antenna design, future growth or changes in mission requirements are unrealistic if the antenna architecture is not matched to the mission during the radar's design. Adding signal processing capability in the future may be possible; however, if the antenna cannot supply the data needed for signal processing, it is useless. The importance of matching mission requirements to radar architecture was demonstrated during the procurement of the Federal Aviation Administration's (FAA's) en route Air Surveillance Radar, Model-4 (ARSR-4) long-range radar. This paper will focus on some of the trade-offs that were made in matching mission requirements to radar design during the acquisition process.

The ARSR-4 is a joint program between the FAA and the United States Air Force (USAF) and is financed through shared funding. In the program's conceptual development, it became quite clear that the different missions of each agency were competing for specific radar architectures. For example, the Air Force's requirements for detecting small radar cross-section targets in high levels of clutter conflicts with the FAA's requirement for few false alarms. Contradictory requirements also existed within each mission, making it impossible to optimize either. An example is the azimuth resolution requirement mandating a narrow beamwidth conflicting with extending the range from the current 200 nmi to 250 nmi, while maintaining a 12-second scan rate. To help alleviate the contradictions that could occur in a design specification, the participants decided to make the contract specification functional in nature rather than to define a specific design.

During conceptual development, it became clear that several mission requirements would drive the system architecture for each user. The Air Force's requirement drivers are low sidelobes, low observable detection over sea clutter, and height accuracy. The FAA's principal requirement drivers are azimuth accuracy and resolution, few false alarms, and detection in rain and terrain clutter. Both agencies agreed that substantial improvements in instrumented range and reduction of false alarms from birds were necessary.

DETECTION OF AIRCRAFT OVER CLUTTER

To meet minimum coverage requirements, probability of detection (P_d) in clutter is specified at 80 percent for all but 5 percent of target

velocities from 20 to 3,000 knots. A probability of detection of 80 percent is specified for each scan at every location where the specified clutter conditions exist, and is not the average of locations with varying magnitudes of clutter interference or the average of all target velocities.

The driving conditions for detection of aircraft with Swerling 1 fluctuation characteristics over surface clutter are summarized below:

<u>Clutter Environment</u>	<u>Target Cross-Section</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Req'd by</u>
Sea state V from 6,500 ft site	0.1 m ²	5-92 nmi	USAF
Mountain reflectivity = -14 dB δ_0	1.0 m ²	5-92 nmi	USAF
Mountain reflectivity = -20 dB δ_0	2.2 m ²	5-180 nmi	FAA
Rain @ 4 mm/hr	2.2 m ²	5-180 nmi	FAA

ANTENNA DESIGN

The first example of system architecture being driven by mission requirements can be seen in the antenna design. Requiring all sidelobes to be -35 dB below the peak on all beams at all frequencies mandated some type of phased-array antenna. Although expensive, phased-array antennas are readily available. The problem occurs when an attempt is made to match a phased-array architecture to mission requirements. For example, most solid state transmitters install their distributed transmitting devices on the planar antenna structure. However, the requirement for only one antenna failure per year drove the ARSR-4 design to a phased-array feed with no active devices and a centralized transmitter below the rotary joint. The requirement for detection in rain also drove the design to circular polarization, which is extremely difficult to incorporate into a planar array.

The phased-array feed on the ARSR-4 is offset from the reflector to avoid blockage. Transmit and receive patterns are formed with approximately 600 horizontally and vertically polarized radiators in 23 rows that are mounted on the cylindrical surface shown in Figure 1. Polarization is automatically selected in 11.25-degree azimuth sectors based on the percentage of the sector filled with rainfall above 3 mm/hr. Right- and left-hand CP echoes are processed: one for aircraft detection, the other for weather.

Figure 1. Small Array: Key to Reliable and Economical Antenna Design.

The selected design combines low azimuth sidelobes with sector switchable vertical/circular polarizations in a simple and economical arrangement. The measured patterns met all expectations, with an over 21 dB integrated cancellation ratio demonstrated across the operating band. Figure 2 is an example of an azimuth pattern taken on the antenna range. Measured sidelobes were more than 35 dB below the peak on all beams at all frequencies, and roll-off was to levels much lower than required.

Figure 2. Low Measured Azimuth Sidelobes.

The elevation coverage is divided among nine receive beams. To achieve height accuracy at long range, the lower beams are narrow in elevation. The higher beams are broader, but the same height accuracy is achieved because aircraft are at shorter ranges in these beams. For selected high elevation sites a look-down transmitter is activated in designated sectors, and a look-down receive beam is substituted for the lowest beam for the first 20 to 30 nmi.

The ARSR-4 dual-stack architecture combines the virtues of simultaneous and sequenced beam schemes while eliminating the weakness of each. At any instant, either a stack of five lower beams or a stack of five upper beams receives and processes echoes. The stacks overlap, so beam 5 is common to both stacks to maintain height-finding accuracy. The advantages of this type of antenna architecture are described in the items below:

- The stacked-beam approach allows more time to process a smooth-velocity response.
- High-stack operation is interleaved without stealing time from the low stack. The "dead time" in the low stack's interpulse period is sufficient for high-stack transmission to provide echoes up to 100,000 feet altitude (133 nmi).
- Surface clutter up to 3 degrees in elevation is rejected over 60 dB by the high stack's two-way elevation sidelobes. This reduces the need for Doppler filtering and reduces transmitted energy and the number of pulses required.

The ARSR-4 coverage from a site at 6,500 feet is shown in Figure 3 for three different aircraft radar cross-sections.

The antenna architecture described in the above paragraphs was dependent on mission requirements not generally associated with antenna engineering. The only requirement usually associated with antenna engineering was the -35 dB sidelobe level requirement. The other detection requirements are usually thought to come under the discipline of signal processing. The important point is that signal processing requirements were more of a factor in determining the antenna's architecture than transmit and receive patterns. Detection requirements in rain and land clutter, coupled with azimuth resolution, reliability, and a 12-second scan rate, were the key elements in driving the design towards 10 stack beams. Because this type of architecture's cost and complexity is

Figure 3. Superior Long-Range Coverage.

great, it would have been impossible to modify an existing radar to add these mission requirements in the future. For this reason, the procuring agency had to specify the radar's mission for the next 20 to 40 years.

SIGNAL PROCESSING

Meeting detection requirements in rain could have been achieved with Moving Target Detection (MTD) processing. However, the requirement to have an 80 percent P_d on 95 percent of all velocities required long dwell times to stagger the MTD pulse batches, a situation that is more attainable on a terminal radar than on a 250 nmi en route radar. To compromise between these conflicting requirements, a design with eight-pulse Doppler filtering and nine interpulse staggers was chosen. The eight-pulse Doppler filtering meets the surface clutter requirements while the circular polarization and the nine-pulse stagger meet the respective detections in rain and velocity response requirements.

The transmitter power level is dictated by the requirement to detect a 2.2 m² aircraft over a mountain at 180 nmi, and a 0.1 m² over sea state V at 92 nmi, where the sensitivity loss of Doppler filtering must be accepted. The correlation of noise by the Doppler filter reduces the number of independent signal-plus-noise samples integrated prior to a detection decision, as the antenna scans past the target. The fraction of the available hits per beamwidth lost due to noise correlation is computed by the method described by Hall and Ward [1], but it can be approximated by the ratio of the width of the clutter rejection notch at a point 6 dB below the peak to the average pulse repetition frequency (PRF). To minimize this width while adequately attenuating clutter requires an optimum clutter notch shape, shown in Figure 4. The optimum shaped notch is achieved by

Figure 4. Superiority of 8-Pulse Doppler Filter over Older 3-Pulse MTI.

an eight-pulse Doppler filter that uses time-varying weights to compensate for the variable interpulse periods. Figure 4 also shows the input and output clutter spectra; the input clutter spectrum includes the effect of antenna scanning modulation and the intrinsic motion of wind-blown foliage on the mountain. The energy in the clutter residue is 63.8 dB below that of the input, ignoring radar instabilities, yet the narrow rejection notch introduces only 1.45 dB of noise-correlation loss.

Although the rejection notch of the older ARSR-3 three-pulse MTI, shown dotted in Figure 4, is wider (measured 6 dB below peak response), indicating higher noise correlation loss (1.65 dB), the response does not drop rapidly enough at lower Doppler frequencies to adequately suppress clutter.

Noise correlation loss represents only a part of the sensitivity loss attributable to Doppler filtering. At certain dim speeds, the Doppler filter attenuates the aircraft echo more than an average amount and causes a velocity response loss. Power must be increased to compensate for these losses at all but the worst 5 percent of aircraft range rates. Figure 5 shows the unusually smooth velocity response of the ARSR-4 (loss of < 1.65 dB at 95 percent of range rates (20-3,000 knots) compared to the ARSR-3 loss of 3 dB).

Figure 5. Unusually Smooth Velocity Response Minimizes Loss at Unfavorable Range Rates.

At the worst dim speed, the loss is only 4 dB, compared to 8 dB in the ARSR-3. This improvement is achieved by:

- Transmitting two frequencies in every pulse, separated by 83 MHz, to stagger the dim speeds.
- Simultaneous reception on a five-beam stack of elevation beams encountering mountain clutter interference, so that full dwell time is available for Doppler filtering, permitting use of nine different interpulse periods. (The ARSR-4 dual-stack architecture was described in a preceding paragraph.)
- Optimum choice of interpulse periods to minimize the depth of dim speed insensitivity, particularly below 300 knots. The smoothest velocity response achievable with N different interpulse periods is produced by an exponential relationship among the interpulse periods, with the longest (IP_{N-1}) nearly twice the shortest (IP_0):

$$IP_n/IP_0 = 2^{*n/N} \quad (1)$$

- Time-varying Doppler filter weights to maintain the desired shape of the clutter rejection notch as the interpulse period varies. The order in which the nine interpulse periods are employed has been chosen to minimize variation in the width of the clutter rejection notch, to maintain consistent clutter attenuation.

Similar stringent constraints are imposed on the Doppler filters to detect 0.1 m² aircraft over sea state V at ranges from 5 to 92 nmi without

increasing transmitter power. Although the backscatter from the sea is substantially weaker than from mountains, it has a broader spectrum with a non-zero mean velocity. The ARSR-4 provides the capability to detect the aircraft under these constraints with:

- A sea/land/coastal land map to select optimum Doppler filters for each type of clutter in 1.4 degree azimuth x 1 nmi range zones.
- Measurement of the mean sea velocity in each 5.6 degree azimuth x 8 nmi range zone and automatic selection of the Doppler filter rejection notch centered within 0.5 knot of the measured velocity.
- Near-sea filters providing maximum attenuation of echoes from a sea state V.
- Far-sea filters that provide acceptable clutter-to-noise attenuation near the horizon (99 nmi from a site at 6,500 feet) where the losses caused by Doppler filtering affect detection of 0.1 m² aircraft.

TRANSMITTER

So far, examples of trade-offs in antenna and signal processing architectures to meet mission requirements have been shown. The last area that will be discussed involves the transmitter. The requirement for an all solid-state, air-cooled transmitter drove the design toward pulse compression, which is the only way to meet range accuracies out to 250 nmi with solid-state devices. This choice, however, developed a new set of problems. For example, reducing time sidelobes required a non-linear FM modulation and a mismatch between the pulse characteristics and the RF front end. Using an FM modulation also developed range bias errors that required a 2.8-degree antenna offset to correct.

The FAA recently upgraded the majority of its older radars with solid-state receivers, but did not include the transmitters for economic reasons. Because the receivers did not include pulse compression processing capability, the transmitters can never be upgraded in the future to all solid state. The lower voltage circuitry could be converted; but without pulse compression, the only way to get the required range would be to use a Klystron type device. This example is just one more case where the complete mission must be considered. Once a radar's architecture is determined, the radar's mission possibilities are also determined.

CONCLUSION

The ARSR-4 architecture combines a unique set of antenna, signal processing, and transmitter designs to meet the different mission requirements of two users. Some of these designs are common to radar engineering while others have never before been utilized. The architecture was developed to meet a broad-based mission that includes both present and future requirements. The program's success is mainly attributed to two important factors. The first factor is that the specification developed was functional in nature without limiting the design to a specific architecture. A functional specification allowed the procuring activity to be creative in predicting future missions. Limiting a mission to current conditions can be fatal because most sophisticated procurement can take up to 15 years to field. The second factor contributing to success was the contractor's expertise in developing a completely new radar architecture that matched mission requirements to system designs. This matching optimized the performance for both agencies even when mission requirements contradicted each other.

ARSR-4 CHARACTERISTICS

Instrumented Coverage	5 to 254 nmi below 100 kft & 30°
Accuracy (RMS)	
Range when $P_0 > 80\%$	1/8 nmi
Azimuth when $P_0 > 80\%$	0.176°
Height on 2.2 m ² aircraft	3 kft to 175 nmi or 100 kft

Resolution of Equal Cross-section	Swerling 1	Aircraft	360° scan period	12 s
Probability of resolution	50%	90%	Mean time between interruption of rotation for repair	Over 1 year
Range separation of aircraft	--	1/8 nmi	Azimuth beamwidth	1.4°
Azimuth separation of aircraft	1.5°	2°	Azimuth sidelobes below peak	> 35 dB
Digital Data Outputs	20 modems, individually programmable format		Elevation transmit beams	High, low, look-down
Target reports	Range, azimuth, height		Elevation receive beams (weather)	4 (V) or 3 (CP)
Weather map	3 levels (30 to 57 dBz)		Elevation receive beams (target)	9 - look-down, 5 simultaneous
Jam strobe report	Azimuth, elevation, amplitude		Receivers/Signal Processors	5 target, 1 weather, 1 spare
Architecture	Dual stacked beams		Dynamic range prior to IF STC	99 dB
Frequency Band	1,215 to 1,400 MHz		Dynamic range after IF STC	63 dB
Frequency Modes Selectable	In 11.25° sectors		A/D converters (I, Q)	12 bits every 72 ns
Diplex	83 MHz separation		Compressed pulsewidth	1.4 μs (6 dB)
Burst agile } Pulse agile }	Random or least jammed	Doppler filtering No Doppler filtering	Dynamic range to point clutter	81 dB
Interpulse Period Modes Selectable	In 11.25° sectors		Range sidelobes below peak	> 30 dB
Variable interpulse period (VIP)	9 IP in low stack		Pulses in Doppler filters	8 or 9
Second-time-around clutter (STAC)	2 IP in low stack		Number of Doppler Filters	Land Coastal Sea
Pulse agile			VIP mode	9 9 9x26
Polarization Modes Selectable	In 11.25° sectors		STAC mode	2 2 2x26
Vertical			False alarm control	
Circular - ICR	> 18 dB		Doppler filter selection	Map plus sea velocity evaluator
Transmitted Waveform	Non-linear FM		Range-averaging CFAR	Editing preserves range resolution
Frequency deviation	1.3 MHz		Two-parameter clutter map	Low & high stack: 1.4° x 1/8 nmi
Stability (Doppler modulation)	Total 68 dBc		Two-parameter weather map	Location & fluctuation of weather
Pulse duration	90+60=150 μs		Geographic censor map	Beams 1 & 2: 1.4° x 1/8 nmi
Average PRF	216 Hz (low stack) 72 Hz (high stack)		Bird editor	Single scan range rate evaluation
Radar Antenna	Array-fed aperture			
Radome diameter	56 ft			
Array size	23 rows; 17 x 12 ft			

REFERENCES

[1] W.M. Hall and H.R. Ward, "Signal-to-Noise Loss in Moving Target Indicator," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, pp. 233-234, February 1968.